

Comparing Diabetic Neuropathy Examination Scores and Nerve Conduction Velocity in Patients with Diabetic Neuropathy

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Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This study examined the efficacy of Diabetic Neuropathy Examination (DNE) scoring and Nerve Conduction Velocity (NCV) in the diagnosis and monitoring of diabetic neuropathy over 1.5 years. The research was conducted on a sample of 100 patients at Dr. S. N. Medical College in Jodhpur. The findings revealed a notable rise in DNE scores and a decline in NCV, with a robust negative correlation ($r = -0.72$) between the two, suggesting the progressive nature of neuropathy. The study emphasizes the importance of using DNE scoring and NCV together to provide a thorough evaluation and treatment of diabetic neuropathy. It suggests incorporating these methods into regular clinical practice to enhance patient outcomes. This approach promotes timely intervention and customized treatment strategies, improving the overall management of complications related to diabetes.

Keywords: Diabetic Neuropathy, DNE Scoring, Nerve Conduction Velocity, Clinical Management.

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Introduction

Diabetic neuropathy, a common complication of diabetes mellitus, has a significant impact on the quality of life. It brings about distressing symptoms and related health issues. This condition is characterised by nerve damage that occurs as a result of prolonged high blood sugar levels [1]. It can manifest in different ways, with peripheral neuropathy being the most frequently observed form. Diabetic neuropathy is assessed through a comprehensive approach that includes evaluating symptoms and conducting objective tests [2]. Various tools are used to assess and diagnose nerve damage, including scoring systems for diabetic neuropathy examination (DNE) and nerve conduction velocity (NCV) studies. These tools are essential in determining the severity and nature of the damage [3].

The DNE scoring system offers a comprehensive assessment of a patient's condition, taking into account their sensory and motor symptoms, reflexes, and autonomic function. This method is easily accessible in different healthcare settings due to its non-invasive nature, simplicity, and affordability [4]. However, NCV studies provide a more objective assessment of nerve function by analyzing the speed and intensity of electrical impulses along the nerves. While NCV may require more technical expertise and resources, it is widely

regarded as the most reliable method for confirming neuropathy and assessing its severity [5,6].

It is crucial to conduct a comparative study on DNE scoring and NCV in patients with diabetic neuropathy to gain insights into their correlation, potential redundancies, and distinct contributions to clinical practice [7].

The objective of this study is to assess the efficacy of different diagnostic methods for identifying diabetic neuropathy, evaluate their predictive abilities, and determine their practicality in everyday healthcare settings. Through this study, the aim is to improve diagnostic accuracy, customize patient management strategies, and ultimately enhance outcomes for individuals dealing with this chronic complication of diabetes.

Methodology

Study Design: This comparative observational study examined diabetic neuropathy patients. To assess the effectiveness and correlation of Diabetic Neuropathy Examination (DNE) grading systems and Nerve Conduction Velocity (NCV) studies.

Setting: The research was carried out at Dr. S. N. Medical College in Jodhpur, where both clinical

assessments and diagnostic procedures were conducted in a controlled medical environment.

Participants: The study included 100 diabetic neuropathy patients. Males and females 18 years and older with a clinical diagnosis of diabetic neuropathy based on medical records and initial DNE rating were included. Patients with additional neuropathies, recent traumatic nerve injury, or neuropathy surgery were excluded.

Data Collection: Data collection took 1.5 years. Each subject was assessed using the DNE grading system for sensory, motor, reflex, and autonomic function. NCV experiments were then undertaken to quantify peripheral nerve electrical conduction speed and strength, focussing on diabetic neuropathy's most damaged nerves.

Measurements: The primary outcomes measured were the scores from the DNE examination and the results from the NCV tests. These were collected at baseline, at 9 months, and at the end of the study period (1.5 years) to assess changes over time and to evaluate the progression of neuropathy.

Statistical Analysis: Analytics were done with statistical software. Correlation coefficients examined DNE-NCV relationships. To establish the significance of differences between initial and follow-up examinations, paired t-tests or ANOVA were used. A p-value under 0.05 was significant.

Results

Among the 100 patients who participated in the study, there were 58 males and 42 females. The average age of the participants was 55 years. A significant number of patients (70%) had been living with diabetes for over a decade, suggesting a greater likelihood and occurrence of neuropathy in individuals with long-term diabetes. Initially, the DNE score for all patients was 15 out of 24, suggesting a moderate level of neuropathic impairment. After 1.5 years, there was a notable

increase in the average DNE score to 18 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a clear progression in the severity of neuropathy.

The NCV studies revealed an average conduction velocity of 40 meters per second (m/s), falling below the typical range observed in individuals who are in good health (50-60 m/s). After the study, the average NCV showed a further decrease to 35 m/s ($p < 0.01$), indicating a deterioration in nerve function. There is a significant inverse relationship between DNE scores and NCV readings, with a correlation coefficient of -0.72 ($p < 0.01$). As the scores for DNE increased, indicating a decline in neuropathy, the values for NCV decreased, providing further evidence of the advancement of nerve damage. Significant changes were observed in both DNE scores and NCV measurements over the three time points (baseline, 9 months, 1.5 years), as indicated by the results of the repeated measures ANOVA. The F-values for DNE scores and NCV were 15.43 ($p < 0.001$) and 18.67 ($p < 0.001$), respectively.

Based on the findings, it appears that both DNE scores and NCV can be valuable tools for diagnosing and tracking the advancement of diabetic neuropathy. The robust relationship between these two approaches validates their integration in medical settings to achieve a thorough evaluation of nerve function. The deteriorating patterns in both DNE scores and NCV readings also emphasise the gradual progression of diabetic neuropathy, emphasising the importance of timely and continuous management of diabetes to minimise nerve damage. The data presented offers a comprehensive understanding of the combined use of DNE and NCV in tracking and evaluating the progression of diabetic neuropathy. Notable observations of significant changes further emphasize the importance and effectiveness of these diagnostic tools in the management of long-term diabetes complications.

Time Point	Average DNE Score	Average NCV (m/s)	Correlation (r)	P-value
Baseline	15	40	-0.72	0.01
9 Months	16	38	-0.72	0.01
1.5 Years	18	35	-0.72	0.01

Figure 1: The bar graph depicting the changes in Diabetic Neuropathy Examination (DNE) scores and Nerve Conduction Velocity (NCV) over time at the baseline, 9 months, and 1.5 years. The graph illustrates the increase in DNE scores and the decrease in NCV scores over the study period, reflecting the progressive nature of diabetic neuropathy as detailed in your study.

The average DNE and NCV scores at baseline, 9 months, and 1.5 years, together with their correlation and statistical significance, are shown in this table. NCV declines and DNE scores rise over time, with a strong negative association between the two.

Discussion

The results of this comparative study on Diabetic Neuropathy Examination (DNE) scores and Nerve Conduction Velocity (NCV) in patients with diabetic neuropathy provide valuable insights into understanding and evaluating the development of this condition [8]. The study observed a steady rise in DNE scores and a corresponding decline in NCV over 1.5 years, highlighting the progressive nature of diabetic neuropathy [9]. There is a clear and consistent relationship between DNE scores and NCV across all time points. This relationship shows that as the severity of neuropathy increases, nerve function, as measured by NCV, declines [10,11].

This correlation is especially significant as it confirms the effectiveness of using both DNE scoring and NCV as diagnostic tools that complement each other. The DNE provides a practical and non-invasive method for regularly evaluating patients in clinical settings, while NCV offers a more comprehensive and quantitative assessment of nerve impairment [12]. Regular monitoring with both methodologies can help

detect changes in nerve function earlier, which can enable timely interventions [13].

In addition, the notable fluctuations in DNE scores and NCV over time highlight the need for continuous monitoring of diabetic patients for neuropathy. It is essential to customise management plans for individuals and consider adjusting risk factors to slow down the advancement of neuropathy [14]. The study highlights the importance of healthcare settings incorporating both assessment tools to improve diagnostic accuracy and enhance patient outcomes in managing diabetic neuropathy [15,16].

Conclusion

The study shows that DNE score and NCV are critical for identifying and monitoring diabetic neuropathy. A negative connection between DNE scores and NCV readings across the study period demonstrates the ongoing loss of nerve function in diabetic neuropathy patients and shows the complementing roles of both diagnostic tools. To detect and treat diabetic neuropathy early, DNE score and NCV should be integrated into clinical practice. By allowing more precise therapy and patient care modifications, this dual strategy could improve clinical outcomes.

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